

Self Contact: Enhancing Virtual Reality Experience Recovering Kinaesthetic Feedback

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Abstract—Despite the considerable technological progress of haptic technology, to date there are still no wearable systems capable of providing both kinaesthetic and cutaneous feedback that are universally recognized and adopted outside the research contexts. This is particularly evident when dealing with virtual reality, where the lack of truthful tactile feedback has often been addressed by exploiting Pseudo-Haptics methods. Being designed to indirectly stimulate the somatosensory system, these methods are not meant to be integrated with haptic devices. With the idea of providing a meeting point between the haptic and pseudo-haptic fields, we propose the *Self Contact* paradigm: exploiting the pseudo-haptic principles to lead the user in generating a real kinaesthetic feedback through the contact between the fingers. *Self Contact* can be implemented alone or in combination with haptic thimbles, allowing to complete the set of tactile stimuli that is necessary for a realistic interaction with virtual objects in pick and place operations. A step-wise validation demonstrated that the proposed approach is suitable for recovering the kinaesthetic feedback into virtual reality, towards the development of increasingly immersive environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The possibility of creating simulated environments modelled on specific requirements has opened new opportunities for both academic and industrial research. Anyway, despite the field of application, the development of convincing scenarios faces the challenge of providing users with consistent sensory inputs. Inducing a persuasive sense stimulation in virtual reality is still an open issue due to technological limitations. To overcome this situation, alternative methods to stimulate tactile perception without directly stimulating the somatosensory system have been studied. These methods fall under the concept of *Pseudo-Haptic Feedback* [1], i.e. the use of visual feedback and properties of human visuo-haptic perception to simulate tactile sensations in virtual environments. In other words, the physical haptic stimulation presented to the users in the virtual environment is different from the one they would perceive through physical contact with objects, but an ad-hoc visual stimulation is able to circumvent this dissimilarity. Following this idea, it is interesting to speculate on how the user experience would change if the visual feedback was made for triggering a real kinaesthetic feedback. In this context, this work proposes the *Self Contact* paradigm: exploiting the Control/Display (C/D) ratio for the virtual hand joint-angle velocity, i.e. the ratio between the human hand velocity and the virtual hand velocity, to let the user make contact between fingers during grasping tasks (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: The user wears a head mounted display and interacts with a virtual object exploiting *Self Contact*. The virtual fingers are in contact with the virtual object when the user’s fingertips are in contact with each other.

II. SELF CONTACT PARADIGM

To make the user perceive a real hand kinaesthetic feedback during a grasping operation, the *Self Contact* paradigm exploits the C/D ratio to slow down the velocity of the virtual hand. Then, the virtual fingers result in contact with the virtual object when the user’s fingertips are in contact with each other, and the kinaesthetic sensation of grabbing an object is restored by the “self contact”. Being a software-based approach, to provide the user with additional cutaneous feedback *Self Contact* can be combined with any haptic thimble by accounting for the device form factor in the computation of the C/D ratio. As a result, this novel approach offers a twofold advantage. On the one hand, it simplifies the implementation of the kinaesthetic feedback in virtual reality, towards more and more realistic experiences. On the other hand, it allows researchers to reduce the encumbrance of wearable haptic technology by embedding in the devices only the hardware needed for providing the cutaneous feedback.

As basic building block, the *Self Contact* algorithm takes advantage of the postural synergies introduced in [2]. Synergies represent a set of linear dependencies between the joint variables of the whole hand, therefore they allow to define the hand posture through a lower number of degrees of freedom. We experimentally assessed that the relationship between the variation of the synergy value and the distance between the virtual index and thumb fingertips can be adequately approximated with a linear function. On the basis of that, we can artificially regulate the virtual hand motion speed by acting on the synergy value.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

To assess the feasibility and the benefits of Self Contact, we conducted a step-wise validation by means of two research questions that have been asked and answered within this work.

a) Does the maximum acceptable C/D ratio change according to the hand velocity assumed by the user?

We define as *maximum acceptable C/D ratio* the maximum scaling factor applicable to the virtual hand joint-angle velocity without affecting the users' perception. To evaluate the ability of humans in discriminating slowed down movements of the hand, a JND experiment was aimed at finding the relationship between joint-angle velocity and maximum acceptable C/D ratio. Several mathematical models interpolating the outcomes of the C/D_{ratio} JND were tested. The logarithmic model was chosen as the most descriptive one. In line with the expectation, the maximum acceptable C/D_{ratio} decreases as the joint-angle velocity increases.

b) Is Self Contact a valid method for providing a kinaesthetic feedback during the interaction with virtual objects?

In an experimental session, participants were asked to perform two-fingers (i.e., thumb and index) pick and place grasps of a virtual cylinder, exploiting 4 different feedback policies aimed at informing the user about the grasping action:

- i) No Feedback (N), no feedback is provided to the user.
- ii) Visual feedback (V), a color change of the cylinder informs the user that the object is grasped.
- iii) Haptic feedback (H), the user interacts with the object exploiting Self Contact.
- iv) Visual and Haptics (VH), both visual and haptic feedback are enabled.

Participants wore plastic thimbles on thumb and index fingertips to reduce the cutaneous feedback component deriving from Self Contact. Task completion time and number of failures were used as metrics for comparing users' performance as the type of feedback modality changes. A failure consisted in a drop of the grasped object while moving it, while the time counter started the first time the object was touched and ended when the object was placed at the goal position.

From the results analysis on the number of failures, it was evident that it was easier to correctly grasp an object when a feedback was given rather than without feedback. What is interesting to highlight is that users found easier to maintain the grasp when the fingertips were in contact. Indeed, the visual feedback only informs the users about the grasp, but does not help them in maintaining the object grasped. Conversely, having the fingertips in contact almost avoids failures in performing the task. For what concerns the completion time, we observed that users spent most of the time in trying to grab the object. As a matter of fact, if the user receives a notification from the environment when the grasp has taken place (i.e., haptic or visual feedback), he/she is faster in grasping the object compared to the case in which the visual feedback relies only to the perspective. As in real situations, the kinaesthetic feedback is meant to inform the user of being in contact with something, which can be the virtual object or the virtual fingertips themselves in the case of an ungraspable object.

c) Users' feedback: At the end of each trial of the previous experiment, participants were requested to fill an online questionnaire which was based on the NASA Task Load Index [3] and extended with a question about the realism of the interaction¹. The resulting questionnaire assesses Mental Demand (MD), Physical Demand (PD), Frustration Level (FR), and Realism (RE) on a 7-point Likert scale.

Firstly, the three answers about the task load (MD, PD, FL) were analysed together. A statistical analysis determined that different feedback strategies elicited statistically significant changes in users' rate. Users' rate decrease was statistically significant from N to all the other feedback strategies, and from V to H and VH, but not from H to VH. Then, the last evaluation was made on users' feedback about the realism of the pick and place task with the four different approaches. Statistically significant differences were found between N and H, and between H and VH. Additionally, the test assessed an increase of realism between V and H, and between V and VH. Statistical analyses on the users' feedback support our hypotheses and confirm the quantitative results obtained in the experiment. The kinaesthetic feedback increases the realism of the interaction, giving the user the perception of grasping something. Such realism is not influenced by the presence of the visual feedback, which remarks that the added value is given by the haptic feedback. Similarly, for what concerns the task load, outcomes demonstrate that receiving a feedback when grasping an object reduces the mental demand and the frustration level, which are the lowest if haptic and visual feedback are combined. Finally, Self Contact reduces the physical demand, which is a reasonable result considering that the contact between fingers helps the user in preserving the position, thus maintaining the grasping becomes easier.

IV. CONCLUSION

Self Contact is a novel approach that exploits pseudo-haptic principles to override the user's kinematic proprioception for recovering kinaesthetic feedback in virtual reality without the need of additional devices. We demonstrated the feasibility of using the visual displacement to guide the user towards making and breaking contact with real surfaces, with a consequent direct stimulation of the somatosensory system. To the best of our knowledge, Self Contact represents the first attempt to create a joining link between the pseudo-haptic and the haptic fields.

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¹The survey is available at <https://www3.diism.unisi.it/~lisini/questionnaires/NASARE.html>